

CONTRIBUTION OF WRITERS FROM ELBASAN IN THE TEMPORARY MAGAZINE “NORMALISTI”

Humanities

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Abstract

In an attempt to make a panoramic reading of the temporary “*Normalisti*”, in a period of eight years, starting from 1929 to 1937, we will look through the protagonists of the writings that will be part of it, is dictated by the object of the theme that was selected from the very beginning. The initiative to publish this object in the press was taken by some students who studied at the school “*Normalisti*”, originally from Elbasan, but not only. In most cases, they will remain in minor writers groups for the history of Albanian literature, but there were some of them like the case of *Sterjo Spasse*, who with his writings became known in larger areas. However, the contribution of the magazine carried weight in the literary life of the city of Elbasan during those years, since the writings were not only of a literary nature. The magazine would contain various articles: including those of a literary nature; didactics; an added value will have the translations, which are characterized by the diversity of some of the names of world classics, as a valuable oasis among all others, etc. It is promoted, mostly the type of novel and narration, while poetry is promoted less, in which the theme of the homeland or the teaching profession predominates. Novels that remind us of Koliqi’s style, with themes that strive to transcend the mentalities of the time. The progress of teaching in the school “*Normalisti*” is reflected through some examples of lessons, called “*Test-lesson*”, which are functionalized in the above-mentioned purpose. The other sections have an educational, literary, linguistic character with folklore content, creating a wider cultural spectrum and diversity for the reader and the nature of the magazine.

Introduction

A temporary is disengaged between literature and journalism, although a newspaper has a more emphasized journalistic nature of writings, in magazines we will always read generously selected literary tastes. We have researched in the magazine “*Normalisti*” the years 1929 - 1937 and we have created approaches regarding the literary world created around it, the nature of the writings, the authors, or the importance of its circulation. From the very beginning, we are informed of the purpose that has motivated the students of the “*Normal*” school to issue a temporary one, *in which they publish any lecture, article, or writing of their own. Willingly to lay a cornerstone in national education and to help all those who will deal with primary education*⁵. In our country, it was an important moment to add a temporary one, through the sacrifices that were encountered to publish them.

On the second page of the first issue, we read an article by the first director of the “*Normale*” school, Aleksandër Xhuvani, who addressed his speech to the students who have undertaken to perform a “*praiseworthy*”⁶ but also a “*difficult*”⁷ task in his opinion, and with the argument *that where primary education flourishes the path of civilization and progress of a nation is paved*.

⁵ *Normalisti*” magazine, our director Sir. A.Xhuvani was appointed general secretary of the Ministry of Education. P.2

⁶ *Ibidem*, p.2

⁷ *Ibidem*

In the third issue of the magazine, in the month of April 1929, an article is dedicated to Aleksandër Xhuvani, who has served for twenty years as the school principal, and they compare him to a steel pole.

Of course, the name of Aleksandër Xhuvani would put the stamp of recognition among his outstanding contribution to Albanian literature, especially that of a linguistic nature, contributing to the further progress of the magazine.

In the issue of 1937, was opened by an article with a didactic nature of A. Xhuvani: “*Të mësuemit e gjânavet të njimëndëta dhe kufini i tyne*”, pp.1-3. Other writers also write about his personality.

❖ What did this Magazine Contain, and who published it?

Since the initiative to publish in the press was taken by the students of the “Normale” school, they bear the burden of preparing and publishing the articles. Apart from them, this temporary became a voice for the teachers of the “Normal” school. Also, there would publish even intellectuals of the time from the city of Elbasan or writers from all over Albania, who studied at the Educational Institute or not, such as *Sterjo Spasse*, who stands out with his frequent writings of a literary, educational nature or through translations, etc.⁸

These writers with their work left traces in Albanian writings, conveying literary and educational values, which were one more voice to keep alive the literary and cultural life of those years. But, not all those who write became well-known voices in our literature, given the writers originating from the city of Elbasan.

❖ Types of Magazine Articles

Defined in temporal and spatial boundaries, this temporary would be for the national culture, and for the reader of that time as a ray of light. We will briefly list the nature of the writings that were published in it:

1. The writings are mostly published in short prose, since we are talking about the writings of the ‘30s; they reflect similarities with those of the other writers of those years, such as the short prose of Koliqi.

⁸ The normalist magazine, in the issue of March 1931 publishes the novel: “*Kreshnikja Shqiptare*”, pp.12-18; In the April 1931 issue, under the heading “*Për tu-mendu*”, he published the article “*Të rijt dhe qytetnimi*”, pp.11-13; January 1932, “*Randësia e mësuemit*”, St. Spasse, pp.4-5; March 1932 “*Vjollca dhe gjembi*”, pp.4-6; February-March 1933 - “*Vjerrsha Vaje e Çajupit*”, pp.16-18; August 1934, in the section “*Kandi Pedagogjik*” – “*Mendimin mbi arësimin filluer*”; “*Kush duron, trashëgon.*” (Victor Hygo), “*As gjâ nuk është e pamundun për njerin që duron*” (Mirabeau-i), “*Kush duron deri në fund, ai i shpëtues ka me qenë*” (Jesu Krishti), St. Spasse, pp.17-18; or in the case of some writings written by the same author under the pseudonym Qukapiku, we find it in several issues: June 1932, Rubric: “*Vjerrsha*”: “*Fullanza*”, p.20; In the section “*Vjerrsha për shkolla fillore*” – “*Djali i mirë*”; Rubric: “*Për t’u çlodhun*”, there are jokes he has collected, etc.

2. The type of novel and story is praised, not only for the space offered by the magazine but also for the fact that they were types of writings that were easily understood by the reader. Poetry is seldom delivered, focusing on the theme of the homeland or the teaching profession.⁹

3. In almost every issue of the magazine, we find some examples of lessons, called “Test-lessons”. As far as it can be noticed, they are in function of the progress of teaching in this school.

4. Also, an added value increased to this periodical is accompanied by translations with limits that were allowed by that time. Selected for publications Translations from temporary foreign languages, such as from French and English, Italian, Persian, are selected for publication, where we need to stand out classical authors, such as: Dante Alighieri, Charles Baudelaire, Grimm Brothers, Alessandro Manzoni, Victor Hugo, Alphonse de Lamartine, and Omar Khayyam, etc.¹⁰

5. The writings are of educational field, about the teaching profession, the theme of the homeland, the theme of love, education in the family and at school, the educational progress, the memories of the teachers, thanks to those who educate, etc.¹¹

6. Other rubrics that also have a literary character are defined by the following titles: ‘*Students’ designs*’, Rubric “*Hither and Thither*” - “*The greeted*”, Rubric “*From our Folklore*”, “*Folk songs*”, “*Folk Legends*”, “*School News*”, “*To relax*”, School news, Foreign news “*Proverbs*”, etc., humorous parts, “*Scientific News*”, “*Pedagogical News*”, etc., creating a variety for the reader of a wider cultural spectrum about the nature of the magazine. In August 1934, a new section was published dedicated to the literary corner entitled “*The New Literary Sound*”.

Instead of closing, we would like to emphasize that the research in the periodical ‘*Normalisti*’ has provided us with another clue to recognize the Albanian writings in general and specifically those published by the writers of the city of Elbasan as a contribution, which will not remain entirely unknown in Albanian letters, published during the years ‘30-‘40.

⁹ “Normalisti” magazine, in section: “Vjersha për shkollë”: 1. Prendvera, 2. I verbëri, H. Zhiti, pp.15-16; January 1932, poem: “E vetmja shpresë” ... Kol Gjetha, p.20; February 1932, “Atdhemohonjësi” poem Kol Gjetha, p.19; Poem, “Prendverës”, Hasan Spahi, Prill 1931 p.26

¹⁰ “Normalisti” magazine, first translation Ali Myftiut “Jean Jacques Rousseau”, June 1935; Rubric “Nga letereatura e huej” Përkt. S. Alliu “Dashuni nane...” Aleksandër Manzoni; June 1936 “I vetmuari”, Baudelaire, p.23; Këpucari i fshatit, VII. Grimm, pp.24-26, translated from Italian Vizi; January 1937 “Nerina”, G. Leopardi, p. 19, translated by Ihsan Podgorica; October 1929, “Dante Alighieri dhe vepra e tij “Divina Commedia” (Komedia Hyjnore)”, Zara, July 30, 1929, H.Dakli pp.6-14, Poezi: “Jetimi”, adapted from Italian by H. Dakli, pp.16-18; August 1934, “Fundosja”, translation from Les Misérables prej S. Caci; May-June 1931 Rubric: ‘Përktime’: “Një ngjarje kusarësh” (Paul-Louis Courier), translated by F. Kekezi, pp.35-38; “Çerdhet e zogjvet”, (Chateaubriand), translated by F.Kekezi, pp.38-39, etc.

¹¹ “Normalisti” magazine, Nasto, V. (“Si mund të gatuhet një e ardhme e mirë”, Q. Shehu, pp. 13-14; po aty, “Miqësi”, Praise friendship, calling it magnificent and divine, a gift from God, the supreme virtue of humanity, betrayal in society is a great shame for humanity, a treasure worth more than any property), June 1929, pp.34-35., Sir. N.Pali, “Nji virtyt i mësuesit, Dashtnia”, pp.2-4, in the same issue “Bujqësia dhe mësuesi” March 1931 p, Ll. Lola., pp.11-12; April 1931 “Ndryshimi ndërmjet të mësimit të vjetër e modern e randësia e dobia e këtij të fundit”, Sh. Islami, pp.1-3; February-March 1933 The school must work for life: for the betterment of human society and its creatures, p. 1-2, Q. Guranjaku; “Nxânsit duhet të ndjejnë një dashuni mësuesin e tyre”, pp.2-5, përmbledhur prej J. Kuvaratit; January 1932, “Shkolla duhet t’edukojë tërthorazi dhe familjen”, Sir. N. Pali, pp.2-3; “Edukata morale”, J. Çeka; Të këqija e papunësisë, S.Caci, August 1934, pp.24-25, etc.

Among them we will mention Aleksandër Xhuvani, Kol Gjetha, Qamil Guranjaku, Eleonora Floqi, Haki Tana, Vangjel Nasto, Varvara Miha, etc., although they can be considered minor writers, this magazine would serve as the basis of a wider culture of writing, but also as a cultural and literary voice important for the tradition of the city of Elbasan.

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